

OPTIMAL PREDICTIVE DESIGN OF BOOLEAN AND ORDER STATISTICS BASED FILTERS

Ioan Tăbuș, Ciprian Doru Giurcăneanu and Jaakko Astola

Tampere University of Technology,

P.O. BOX 553, Tampere 33101, FINLAND

Tel: +358 3 3653911; fax: +358 3 3653857

e-mail: {tabus,cipriand,jta}@cs.tut.fi

ABSTRACT

This paper first reviews several techniques for optimal predictive design of Boolean and L-filters, which proved successful in lossless audio and image compression[3][7][9]. We show that two well known nonlinear predictors, namely the Median Adaptive Predictor and the Gradient Adaptive Predictor, which are used in state of the art lossless compression are particular cases of our FSM-L predictors. Including the GAP predictor parameters as initial conditions in our adaptive FSM-L prediction scheme is shown to consistently improve the compression performance, with no increase in the overall complexity.

1 INTRODUCTION

Boolean and order statistics filters have proven a very efficient alternative to linear filters in noise removal applications, especially for impulsive noise. However, an equally important role may be assumed by the nonlinear filters in other applications, e.g. lossless image compression, where the nonlinear predictors were shown to perform well; furthermore, the most well known predictors for lossless image compression, introduced based on various heuristics, are shown here to be simply Boolean predictors, or particular cases of the FSM-L filters introduced in [9].

The optimal predictive design is a crucial problem for lossless signal compression applications. At each sample (or pixel) site t , the encoder performs the prediction $\hat{x}_t$ of the n -bit signal x_t , and then encodes the value of the prediction error $\varepsilon_t = x_t - \hat{x}_t$. The decoder at its side performs the reversed process: decodes the prediction error and then adds it to the predicted value to perfectly restore the sample value x_t . The code length to be used at site t is $-\log P(\varepsilon_t | \text{“context at”}t)$, and therefore the most natural optimality criterion is the entropy of the prediction errors. The optimal solution for the above problem is found by the Context algorithm[11], which unfortunately has a complexity exponential in the number of alphabet symbols. To keep the algorithm at a reasonable complexity, context based prediction has been used [11][12], where the context tree structure is used to select between different linear predictors. However, a context tree structure combined with nonlinear predictors offers more flexibility, and clearly encompasses the context base linear predictors as particular cases[9]. The general prediction structure contains a tree (or more general a finite state machine) for context selection and adaptive predictors whose parameters are associated to the nodes in the tree.

2 A CLASS OF NONLINEAR ADAPTIVE PREDICTORS

We start by reviewing here, based on [3][7][9] the basic framework for predictive design of Boolean filters.

We will introduce several different sequential predictors here, all being related to the thresholding architecture (a common feature for some nonlinear filter classes, e.g. order statistics filters, stack filters or Boolean filters [8]). The basic scheme of Boolean filters is the following: decompose the N pixel prediction mask $\underline{X} = [X_1 \dots X_N]$ into N binary prediction masks $\underline{v}^{(1)}, \dots, \underline{v}^{(N)}$, by comparing in turn the entries in $\underline{X}$ with each order statistic $X_{(1)}, \dots, X_{(N)}$ of the samples. (We let $X_{(0)} = 0$ and $X_{(N+1)} = 2^n - 1$). Then the prediction in each of the binary masks is performed, to get $f(\underline{v}^{(1)}), \dots, f(\underline{v}^{(N-1)})$ and finally they are combined to give the prediction of x_t as follows:

$$\hat{x}_t = f(\underline{v}^{(0)})X_{(1)} + \sum_{k=1}^N f(\underline{v}^{(k)})(X_{(k+1)} - X_{(k)}) \quad (1)$$

2.1 An example of fixed (nonadaptive) Boolean predictor: Martucci’s predictor

Martucci’s predictor [5][10] is well known by its definition

$$\hat{x} = \text{median}(X_w, X_n, X_w + X_n - X_{nw}) \quad (2)$$

where compass-like notations are used, e.g. $X_w = X(i-1, j)$, $X_n = X(i, j-1)$ and $X_{nw} = X(i-1, j-1)$. The predictor output will be one of the values X_w , X_n or $X_w + X_n - X_{nw}$, depending on the order of the samples X_w, X_n, X_{nw} .

The edge selective behaviour of the predictor can be explained as follows: the predictor uses the optimal linear fit $\hat{x} = X_w + X_n - X_{nw}$ when the image is smooth, while when edges are present the planar prediction becomes strongly biased by the outlier, making more attractive the one pixel predictions $\hat{x} = X_w$ or $\hat{x} = X_n$, depending on the apparent direction of the edge.

Consider the Boolean function $f(x_1x_2x_3) = x_1\bar{x}_3 + x_2\bar{x}_3 + x_1x_2$ having the truth table representation $\underline{f} = [0 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 0 \ 1 \ 1]$ and the Hasse diagram in Figure 1.

Taking into account all possible orderings of the three pixels, we show in Table 1 that Martucci’s predictor can be equivalently expressed as the Boolean filter associated to $f(x_1x_2x_3)$. Therefore it is a particular case of the FSM-L predictor[9], where all main contexts collapse to a single node.

Inequalities	Prediction
$X_w \leq X_n \leq X_{nw}$	$\hat{x} = X_w + f([011])(X_n - X_w) + f([001])(X_{nw} - X_n) = X_w$
$X_w \leq X_{nw} \leq X_n$	$\hat{x} = X_w + f([011])(X_{nw} - X_w) + f([010])(X_n - X_{nw}) = X_w + X_n - X_{nw}$
$X_n \leq X_w \leq X_{nw}$	$\hat{x} = X_n + f([101])(X_w - X_n) + f([001])(X_{nw} - X_w) = X_n$
$X_n \leq X_{nw} \leq X_w$	$\hat{x} = X_n + f([101])(X_{nw} - X_n) + f([100])(X_w - X_{nw}) = X_w + X_n - X_{nw}$
$X_{nw} \leq X_w \leq X_n$	$\hat{x} = X_{nw} + f([110])(X_w - X_{nw}) + f([010])(X_n - X_w) = X_n$
$X_{nw} \leq X_n \leq X_w$	$\hat{x} = X_{nw} + f([110])(X_n - X_{nw}) + f([100])(X_w - X_n) = X_w$

Table 1: Martucci’s predictor equivalently written as the Boolean filter $\hat{x}_f$ with $\underline{f} = [0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 1\ 1]$

Figure 1: Martucci’s predictor equivalently drawn as the Boolean filter $\hat{x}_f$ with $\underline{f} = [0\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 1\ 0\ 1\ 1]$

2.2 Adaptive Boolean predictors

The adaptive Boolean predictors may be characterized by three important features: different predictors are used for different conditioning contexts, the decision rules may be hard or soft, deterministic or randomized, and finally, the updating of the counters is realized in an adaptive manner. We will represent all the adaptive characteristics of the predictor by a Finite State Machine (FSM) structure having some counters and parameters associated with its nodes. Our FSM will parse the sequence of pixels in the prediction mask or some previous prediction errors, resulting in the sequence of FSM nodes labeled with $\underline{v}^{(0)}, \underline{v}^{(1)}, \dots, \underline{v}^{(N)}$. The parameters associated with the sequence of nodes will be used to compute the actual prediction. The FSM itself, the counters and the parameters associated with its nodes at time t are denoted by $\mathcal{F}^t$. The value of the prediction will be computed generalizing the Boolean predictor as follows

$$\hat{x}_t^B = \sum_{k=1}^{N+1} \hat{y}(\underline{v}^{(k-1)} |_{\mathcal{F}^{t-1}, \underline{X}, \varepsilon_{t-1}})(X^{(k)} - X^{(k-1)}) \quad (3)$$

The errors incurred at each binary prediction level can be further compensated taking into account their accumulated bias in the overall prediction error. Therefore we will extend the Boolean predictor with an extra term that can be adapted using the errors at integer level, resulting in the overall prediction

$$\hat{x}_t = \rho(\underline{v}^{(1)}, \dots, \underline{v}^{(N-1)} |_{\mathcal{F}^{t-1}, \underline{X}, \varepsilon_{t-1}}) + \sum_{k=1}^{N+1} \hat{y}(\underline{v}^{(k-1)} |_{\mathcal{F}^{t-1}, \underline{X}, \varepsilon_{t-1}})(X^{(k)} - X^{(k-1)}) \quad (4)$$

where the term $\rho(\underline{v}^{(1)}, \dots, \underline{v}^{(N-1)} |_{\mathcal{F}^{t-1}, \underline{X}, \varepsilon_{t-1}})$ will compensate adaptively for the bias of the *sum* of Boolean predictions. The following subsections describe in detail the features of

adaptive Boolean predictors and specify several predictors in the class (3) which we tested in our experiments.

The Order Statistics based context selection

We select a primary conditioning context for the predictors by quantizing two different variables: one accounts for the order statistics of the samples inside the prediction mask and the last one depends on the recent error(s).

We also define a secondary context, which is naturally demanded by the Boolean prediction architecture, and takes into account the order of the pixels inside the processing window. At each primary context node s_{m_i} , the secondary context selects the proper values for the binary vectors $\underline{v}^{(1)}, \underline{v}^{(2)}, \dots, \underline{v}^{(N-1)}$, and for the counters $N(0 |_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}})$ and $N(1 |_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}})$.

The overall context FSM $\mathcal{F}$ is obtained by concatenating one secondary FSM at each leaf of the primary context tree. The prediction model to be used is found generating a path in the FSM as follows. At each pixel x_t a path in the FSM is found, starting from the root and ending at the maximum depth node, by answering all questions on the branches. The path at the pixel x_t will be denoted by $path_t = (\underline{v}^{(0)}, s_{m_i}, \dots, (\underline{v}^{(N)}, s_{m_i}))$. The basic elements needed to compute the prediction (3) are: the primary context leave s_{m_i} , the binary vectors $\underline{v}^{(k)}$, and their associated counters $N(0 |_{\underline{v}^{(k)}, s_{m_i}})$, $N(1 |_{\underline{v}^{(k)}, s_{m_i}})$, corresponding to the nodes in the (secondary context) path. Different predictor variants using this basic contextual information will be described in the following.

Probability assignment for the thresholded binary sequence

The counts $N(0 |_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}})$ and $N(1 |_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}})$ corresponding to a given node in $\mathcal{F}^{t-1}$, are used to compute the conditional probability assignment. When a binary sequence is given with N_1 occurrences of 1 and N_0 occurrences of 0, the probability of the next occurrence of 1 can be estimated in several ways.

The following estimators are considered:

$$p_{ML}(1 |_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}}) = \frac{N(1 |_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}})}{N(0 |_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}}) + N(1 |_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}})} \quad (5)$$

maximum likelihood off-line estimator;

$$p_{KT}(1 |_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}}) = \frac{N(1 |_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}}) + 0.5}{N(0 |_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}}) + N(1 |_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}}) + 1} \quad (6)$$

Krichevski – Trofimov probability estimator[4];

$$p_L(1 |_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}}) = \frac{N(1 |_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}}) + 1}{N(0 |_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}}) + N(1 |_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}}) + 2} \quad (7)$$

Laplace rule of succession[6].

Each of the above estimate can be further processed to obtain several nonlinear estimates, as follows

$$p_F(1|_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}}) = \frac{F(p(1|_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}}))}{F(1 - p(1|_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}})) + F(p(1|_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}}))} \quad (8)$$

where $p()$ is one of the estimates (5)–(7) and F is a sigmoidal function, e.g.

$$F(x) = -\log(1 - x) \quad (9)$$

or the piecewise linear function:

$$F(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & x < \frac{1}{2} - \Delta \\ \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2\Delta} (x - \frac{1}{2}), & \frac{1}{2} - \Delta \leq x \leq \frac{1}{2} + \Delta \\ 1, & \frac{1}{2} + \Delta < x. \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

The performance under absolute loss of these predictors for binary sequences has been analyzed in [1]. We have trained the parameter Δ in the piecewise linear transformation (10) for a large set of images and in [7] are reported the values obtained with the estimator (8),(10) which was shown to perform the best.

Three prediction algorithms

Adaptive Hard Boolean Predictor

The predictor (4) will be referred to as adaptive hard Boolean predictor when the binary prediction will be computed as

$$\hat{y}^{hard}(\underline{v}|_{\mathcal{F}^{t-1}, \underline{x}, \varepsilon_{t-1}}) = \begin{cases} 0, & p(1|_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}}) \leq \frac{1}{2} \\ 1, & \frac{1}{2} > p(1|_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}}). \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Note that all estimates (5)–(8) will give the same result when used in (11).

Adaptive Soft Boolean Predictor

The threshold decomposition with binary values for $\hat{y}_t \in \{0, 1\}$ in (3) can be further generalized to real values $\hat{y}_t \in [0, 1]$. The expected value of the hard binary prediction $\hat{y}_t^{hard}$ is

$$E\hat{y}_t^{hard}(\underline{v}|_{\mathcal{F}^{t-1}, \underline{x}, \varepsilon_{t-1}}) = p(1|_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}}) \quad (12)$$

The predictor (4) will be referred to as adaptive soft Boolean predictor when the expectation (12) will be adopted as optimal soft binary prediction

$$\hat{y}_t^{soft}(\underline{v}|_{\mathcal{F}^{t-1}, \underline{x}, \varepsilon_{t-1}}) = p_F(1|_{\underline{v}, s_{m_i}}) \quad (13)$$

where we adopted the more flexible probability estimator (8). The change from (11) to (13) will prove to be essential in improving the performances of the coding scheme.

Adaptive Randomizing Boolean Predictor

We consider next the prediction of the binary value, based on a stochastic rule. The rationale behind this is to adopt hard, deterministic decision when the 0- and 1- counts differ significantly, and to randomize the decision when the difference between 0- and 1- counts is small. Adopting the randomizing interval to be $[\frac{1}{2} - \Delta, \frac{1}{2} + \Delta]$ (centered at $p(1|_{y^t}) = 1/2$), the prediction rule can be stated

$$Prob(\hat{y}^{rand}(\underline{v}^{(k-1)}|_{\mathcal{F}^{t-1}, \underline{x}, \varepsilon_{t-1}}) = 1) = p_F(1|_{\underline{v}^{(k-1)}, s_{m_i}}) \quad (14)$$

When a time dependent length of the randomizing interval in (10) is adopted, i.e. $\Delta_t = 1/(2\sqrt{t} + 2)$, the predictor (14) is shown in [2] to approach the predictability of the best

Figure 2: The notations of the pixels in the template, and gradient definitions

single state predictor, universally for all sequences, at a rate $\mathcal{O}(1/\sqrt{t})$. The adaptive randomizing Boolean predictor will be obtained using the randomized binary prediction in (4).

We summarize here the adaptive Boolean prediction, making use of the conditional contexts defined by the FSM $\mathcal{F}$. The predictor (4) is computed as

$$\hat{x}_t = \rho(path_t) + \sum_{k=1}^{N+1} \hat{y}(\underline{v}^{(k-1)}, s_{m_i})(X_{(k)} - X_{(k-1)}) \quad (15)$$

2.3 Gradient Adaptive Predictor as a context based soft Boolean predictor

Let us define the three pixel gradient adaptive predictor

$$\hat{x} = \begin{cases} X_w & G_o \geq 80 \\ X_n & G_o \leq -80 \\ X_{planar} = X_w + X_n - X_{nw} & -80 \leq G_o \leq 80 \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

where the gradient G_0 can be estimated by any of the gradients G_n, G_w, G_{nw}, G_{ne} defined in Figure 2. This predictor is seen to be the simplest generalization of Martucci's predictor to include the contexts selected according to the quantization of G_0 to three regions.

In [12] the following gradient adaptive predictor was introduced: the gradient was estimated as $g = G_n + G_w + G_{ne}$ and then the prediction contexts were defined by the interval in which g falls: $(-\infty - 80), [-80, 32), [-32, -8), [-8, 8), [8, 32), [32, 80), [80, \infty)$. At each prediction context a different linear predictor is used[12]. We present in Figure 3 the FSM-L predictor realizing exactly the same function as GAP.

3 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

In Table 2 we list the results obtained by using several prediction methods discussed in this paper for lossless image compression. The results of LOCO-I which uses Martucci's fixed predictor are taken from [10] (we note that after some changes LOCO-I became the new lossless compression standard JPEG-LS). The results for CALIC[12], which uses GAP predictor are obtained with the demonstration program made public by the authors. The results of ASBOSC, which uses a finite state machine context selection and the adaptive soft prediction (13), is taken from [7]. The first column, showing the best compression result, is obtained by changing the prediction of [7] to initialize the adaptive soft predictors with the parameters of the GAP predictors as defined in Figure 3.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Adaptive Boolean and L-predictors for various context selection rules prove a rich family providing the state-of-the-art performance in lossless image coding. Experimenting all different predictors, with the same context modeller and coder,

Figure 3: Tree implementation of GAP predictor: $g = G_w + G_n + G_{ne}$ selects the primary context; each Hasse diagram defines the soft Boolean predictor (the value in the node labeled by $\underline{v}$ represents $f(\underline{v})$ multiplied by $f([1\ 1\ 1\ 1])$). At the primary context node $-32 \leq g < -8$ the Hasse diagram is identical to that at the node $8 \leq g < 32$, except the variables X_w is interchanged with X_n . With the same interchange we obtain the Hasse diagram at the node $-80 \leq g < -32$ from the diagram at $32 \leq g < 80$.

	GAP + ASBOSC	ASBOSC	CALIC	LOCO-I
barb1	4.252	4.289	4.413	4.65
barb2	4.482	4.473	4.530	4.66
balloon	2.786	2.807	2.825	2.90
girl	3.698	3.709	3.767	3.90
hotel.y	4.257	4.227	4.249	4.35
boats	3.751	3.762	3.834	3.92
gold.y	4.382	4.377	4.394	4.47
zelda	3.654	3.699	3.750	3.87
Average	3.908	3.918	3.970	4.09

Table 2: Comparison of compression (bits/pixel) for several Context based lossless image coding methods

will reveal that only small or moderate differences in coding rate are obtained by increasing the complexity of the predictor.

Recent progress has been achieved in universal prediction, universal compression and universal modelling, but the main results and applications assume linear regression models. In our view, exploring the capabilities of various classes of nonlinear filters under universal prediction framework is one challenge which is worth accepting.

References

- [1] N. Cesa-Bianchi, D.P. Helmbold, and S. Panizza. On Bayes methods for on-line boolean prediction. In *Proceedings of the 9th Annual Conference on Computational Learning Theory*, pages 314–324. ACM Press, 1996.
- [2] M. Feder, N. Merhav, and M. Gutman. Universal Prediction of Individual Sequences. *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, IT-38:1258–1270, July 1992.
- [3] C-D Giurcăneanu, I. Tăbuș, and J. Astola. Adaptive context based sequential prediction for lossless audio compression. In *EUSIPCO-98*, pages 2349–2352, Island of Rhodes, Greece, Sep 1998.
- [4] R.E. Krichevsky and V.K. Trofimov. The performance of universal encoding. *IEEE Transactions on Information Theory*, IT-27:199–207, Mar. 1981.
- [5] St. Martucci. Reversible compression of HDTV images using median adaptive prediction and arithmetic coding. In *Proc. IEEE Int. Symp. Circ. Sys.*, pages 1310–1313, New Orleans, Louisiana, 1990.
- [6] E. Parzen. *Modern probability theory and its applications*. John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 1960.
- [7] I. Tăbuș and J. Astola. Adaptive Boolean predictive modelling with application to lossless image coding. In *SPIE - Statistical and Stochastic Methods for Image Processing II*, pages 234–245, San Diego, California, Jul. 1997.
- [8] I. Tăbuș, D. Petrescu, and M. Gabbouj. A training framework for stack and Boolean filtering-Fast optimal design procedures and robustness case study. *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing Special Issue on Non-linear Image Processing*, IP-5:809–826, June 1996.
- [9] I. Tăbuș, J. Rissanen, and J. Astola. Adaptive L-predictors based on finite state machine context selection. In *Proc. ICIP'97 International Conference on Image Processing*, pages 401–404, Santa Barbara, California, Oct. 1997.
- [10] M. Weinberg, G. Seroussi, and G. Sapiro. LOCO-I a low complexity, context-based, lossless image compression algorithm. In *Proc. DCC'96 Data compression conference*, pages 140–149, Snowbird, Utah, Mar. 1996.
- [11] M. Weinberger, J. Rissanen, and R. Arps. Applications of universal context modeling to lossless compression of gray-scale images. *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, IP-5:575–586, Apr. 1996.
- [12] X. Wu and N. Memon. Context-based, adaptive, lossless image codec. *IEEE Transactions on Communications*, Comm-45:437–444, April 1997.